

Supplement 3: Occurrence of U-*mecA*, *mecA*, and *mecA1* in PBS-rinse samples of bulk milk (BM)

Figure 1-S3 Example of U-*mecA*-detection in PBS-rinse-samples of bulk milk..... 1

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Of 204 PBS-rinse samples, 96 tested positive for U-*mecA*. Among these, 27 BMS were U-*mecA* positive in both plate enrichment samples (Col and BP). In 32 BMS, only the Col-enrichment sample tested positive for U-*mecA*, while in 10 cases, only the BP enrichment sample was positive. In total, the positive results were associated with 69 BMS. Among the 32 U-*mecA* positive Col enrichment-samples, 5 samples tested positive for specific *mecA*, 16 samples tested positive for *mecA1*, 4 were positive for both *mecA* and *mecA1*, and 7 samples tested negative for both targets. For the ten U-*mecA* positive BP enrichment- samples, 3 samples tested positive for *mecA* and 7 samples were positive for *mecA1*

Figure 1-S3 Example of U-*mecA*-detection in PBS-rinse-samples of bulk milk
 The figure shows the U-*mecA* detection (Primer No. 1; 525 bp) in PBS-rinse-samples of BM. (+) = PCR-positive control (MRSA 28766); (-) = PCR-negative control; Number of BMS = 42 – 48; c = Col-PBS-rinse sample; b = BP-PBS-rinse-sample.

Table 1-S3 Number of *U-mecA/mecA/mecA1*-positive BMS based on results of corresponding PBS-rinse samples after plate enrichment

Target gene	Per bulk milk samples (n=102)	Per total number of PBS rinse samples of agar plates (BP and Columbia) (n=204)
<u>U-mecA detected in:</u>		
Col + BP	27	54
- only <i>mecA</i> ^a	- 4	
- only <i>mecA1</i> ^b	- 13	
- <i>mecA</i> & <i>mecA1</i>	- 10	
Only Col	32	32
- only <i>mecA</i>	- 5	
- only <i>mecA1</i>	- 16	
- <i>mecA</i> & <i>mecA1</i>	- 4	
- neither <i>mecA</i> , nor <i>mecA1</i>	- 7	
Only BP	10	10
- only <i>mecA</i>	- 3	
- only <i>mecA1</i>	- 7	
- <i>mecA</i> & <i>mecA1</i>	- 0	
In total	69 (67.65%)	96
<u>specific <i>mecA</i> detected in:</u>		
Col + BP (Primer No. 3 / No. 4)	0 / 9	0 / 18
Col (Primer No. 3 / No. 4)	1 / 11	1 / 11
BP (Primer No. 3 / No. 4)	8 / 6	8 / 6
in total (Primer No. 3 / No. 4)	9 (8.8%) / 26 (25.49%)	9 / 35
<u>specific <i>mecA1</i>^c detected in:</u>		
Col + BP	13	26
Col	22	22
BP	15	16
In total	50 (49.02%)	64

The milk samples were plated on Col and BP agar plates, rinsed off, and analyzed using PCR. A milk sample was considered positive for the respective target gene if the gene was detected in at least one of the corresponding PBS rinse sample (Col or BP). The table shows the composition of the total number of gene-positive milk samples: Col + BP = the target gene was detected in both rinsing samples (Col and BP) of the milk sample. Only Col = the target gene was detected exclusively in the Col rinse sample, but not in the BP rinse sample. Only BP = the target gene was detected exclusively in the BP rinse sample, but not in the Col rinse sample. In the case of *U-mecA*, further differentiation was made regarding which specific gene (*mecA* or *mecA1*) was detected in the *U-mecA* positive sample. Six Col-PBS-rinse samples were *U-mecA* positive, but neither *mecA* nor *mecA1* could be detected. As the corresponding BP sample was *mecA* (n=2) or *mecA1* (n=4) positive, the milk sample was counted as “*U-mecA* Col + BP positive” and “only *mecA*” or “only *mecA1*” positive (footnote a & b).

- a) In 2 milk samples, only the BP-PBS-rinse sample was *mecA* positive. The corresponding Col sample was U-*mecA* positive but neither *mecA* nor *mecA1* could be detected.
- b) In 4 milk samples, only the BP-PBS-rinse sample was *mecA1* positive. The corresponding Col sample was U-*mecA* positive but neither *mecA* nor *mecA1* could be detected.
- c) detected with primer No. 6 (this study), (checked with primer No. 5 if the sample was *mecA* positive as well)